

ANALYSIS OF SUSTAINABLE INTERMODAL TRANSPORTATION: CASE STUDY OF MIHAIL KOGĂLNICEANU CONSTANȚA AIRPORT

S. E. ZAHARIA, C. V. PIETREANU*

*Aerospace Engineering Department, Politehnica University of Bucharest, Polizu Street 1-7, Sector 1, Bucharest 011061, Romania
E-mail: cassandra.pietreanu@yahoo.com*

Abstract. The paper presents an assessment of the integration of Mihail Kogălniceanu Constanța Airport in the regional and national intermodal transport network and the impact on the environment of the airport infrastructure development. A research on freight and passenger transport demand on the market in parallel with transport infrastructure development and the investment for transforming the airport into an intermodal node, represent the cornerstone for the authors' proposal. The research method represents an integrated approach between transport systems such as: road, rail, sea and air services. Economic and social impact will also be analyzed to ensure a sustainable development. Meeting the needs of accessibility and mobility, the analysis will underlie that investments in airport infrastructure represent a development pole local and regional wide. The outcome of intermodal transport growth will be reflected at the level of all environmental factors. Adapting to new operational technologies regarding transport modes for multimodal commuting implies respecting the principles of sustainable development. Thus, an analysis of the internal/external environment of the airport will be accomplished for implementing environmental policy and the management of protected areas. The authors develop solutions for environmental impact reduction, accordingly to the goals of Flightpath 2050.

Keywords: environmental impact, green supply chain management, intermodal transport network, sustainable development

AIMS AND BACKGROUND

The paper presents a proposal for implementing an intermodal network to reduce transportation impact on the environment accordingly to the goals of Flightpath 2050 whose implementation was analyzed in the PARE project. Our analysis will consider Mihail Kogălniceanu Airport as the core of the transport network, and will imply an integrated approach between rail, sea and air transport systems. The research airport was chosen for its geostrategic position towards national/international economic objectives and the connection with important road and rail transport routes. Thus, economic and social aspects will be analyzed to ensure a sustainable development of the region, since Constanța is the second largest Black Sea port in the EU and an important commercial, industrial and touristic center. In the light of the above mentioned, a correlation between economic and transport growth will be outlined.

Romanian economy has met a slight increase in recent years.

Fig. 1 Romania's economic growth (1996-2017) and evolution of GDP (2005-2017) (source: based on NIS data⁷)

GDP growth, low public debt and favourable price-skilled workforce ratio make the country attractive to foreign investments^{9,16} (Fig.1). The figures above show GDP growth from 3.7% in 2015 to 7% in 2017. The S-E Region shows the following evolution of the GDP over the last 6 years (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. GDP in S-E Region (2012-2017) (source: based on NIS data⁷)

Although the S-E region presents the highest number of economically inactive or unemployed persons, it is also the second most developed in terms of the share of workers in the service sector, with a total labor force of 16.2%⁵. The National Institute of Statistics shows that Constanța and the SE Region are on the third place nationally regarding the lowest number provided of skilled and assimilated workers in Romania (i.e. 12.12% of the total)⁷.

The industry of the county relies on shipbuilding, construction materials, woodworking, textile and a medium developed chemical and petrochemical sector. However, the food industry holds a leading place in the county economy, with fish, oil, dairy products, fruit or vegetable juices and wine. The foreign investments target manufacturing industry for food, wood products, machinery, metallurgy, chemical products processing, or trade, construction and real estate transactions. The S-E region's value of the foreign investment balance is 3800 million euros, occupying the 6th position in the list of investments in our country (i.e. 5%)⁵.

Mihail Kogălniceanu International airport (MKIA), located in Constanța County, has a geostrategic position, 14 km from the Danube-Black Sea Canal¹⁵. MKIA's activity is in connection with the economic development of the region. In 2017, the airport registered a profit of 1,942,285 lei, transferring 310,766 lei worth taxes to the Romanian state¹⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL

An extensive documentation regarding freight and passenger transport demand on the market and transport infrastructure development underlies the authors' research. Discussions with specialists in intermodal transport, exponents of Romanian authorities in air transport and in-situ meetings with representatives of the airport concerned, served as a way to identify the need for investments in infrastructure for developing optimal intermodal transport network.

The research explores the opportunities for MKIA intermodal infrastructure development and proposals for environmental impact reduction and green supply chain management. The solutions for a unified transport market respect the principles of sustainable development.

The transport modes distribution in the caption area shows the next ranking: road, rail, fluvial and air transport, with an insignificant difference between the first two, and a 16% difference between road and air transport modes. In Constanța County, in the last decades, cargo transport noticed a shift towards road traffic and barges, to the detriment of rail.

Constanța Harbor, situated 179 nautical miles from the Bosphorus Strait, is significant for its role in the European intermodal transport network due to its location, connecting the CEE countries with Central Asia and the Far East⁸. Although is considered to have a marginal

percentage on impacting merchant voyages, meteorological conditions implying high wind speed in Constanța harbor affect marine navigation, hindering ships maneuvers³.

The Danube-Black Sea Canal is insufficiently used for freight transport, so building a cargo center would involve a reduction in road transport and a low grade of damage for road infrastructure. An increase in cargo transportation must consider the shipping market and must involve adapting the policies and management decisions to the world change⁴. The opportunities to develop intermodal transport at Constanța Harbor are given by proper link with combined transport and the potential to handle various types of cargo.

However, regarding the necessity analysis for cargo promotion, it can be noticed that at present, the development opportunities are reduced. Products exported through this channel are few, for example Dacia spare parts sent to Brazil, naval construction, coal and lignite, refined from petroleum, agricultural products or few perishable shipments. Yet, studies show that regarding cargo transport, we can be interesting for Poland, Hungary and Moldova.

A problem raised by combined transport modes considers customs transit for extra-community goods. High duration of customs control may result in damaging perishable goods. Harbor transport shows the following share: Constanța (80.5%), Midia (15.4%) and Galați (2.7%), and for inland waterways transport, Constanța occupies the first place with 47% of the share, followed by Galați – 33.4%⁷. Although only national inland waterway transport has grown by 10.3%, this was reflected in an overall increase of 2.3% (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Inland waterway cargo indicators (2017-2018) (source: based on NIS data⁷)

In 2018, Romania experienced a 7.9% growth in the transport of goods (freight and mail) by air, figures indicating 48.520 tonnes⁷. At the same time, cargo transportation from Mihail Kogălniceanu International Airport does not rebate from the ones previously established, so freight transport is almost insignificant, coming from non-scheduled international flights in June (63 tones) and August (10 tones)¹⁵. Unlike Henri Coandă Otopeni Airport, Avram Iancu Cluj, Traian Vuia Timișoara and others, MKIA did not transport any domestic goods in 2018.

Table 1. Cargo analysis at MKIA (2018)

Type of flight	Domestic scheduled	Domestic non-scheduled	International scheduled	International non-scheduled
Freight (tones)	0	0	0	73

Table 1 indicates that there are no opportunities for cargo development. However, MKIA can become a transit airport to Asia and the Orient, transporting for example sheep and goats.

In 2018, the airports in Romania were transited by 21,858,724 pax, (7.76% increase from 2017)⁶. Henri Coandă Airport still has the largest number of transported passengers (i.e. 13,820,428)⁶. A 1.3 % increase in passenger traffic was noticed in 2018 at MKIA, compared to 2017, coming in the 10th place in the contribution to Romanian airports passenger traffic. The modest passenger volume is due to low frequencies of domestic and international flights.

Although Constanța is an affordable destination by air, thanks to the ticket prices offered by low-cost carriers, the demand is unsatisfactory partly due to the variety of flights on Henri Coandă International Airport, which is not far from Constanța (apx. 3 hours drive). Travel agencies usually promote flights to/from Bucharest, due to the complete offer of flights offered by OTP. Another threat comes from Varna and Burgas airports in Bulgaria which have met an important development in recent years since they were owned by Fraport.

Regulated internal flights in the estival season totalize 20.423 tourists from Cluj, Oradea, Timișoara (flights operated by Blue Air) and Satu Mare-with Tarom¹⁵, as exposed in Table 2.

Table 2. MKIA number of passengers from domestic/international flights (2018)

Type of flight	Aircraft movements	Embarked pax.	Disembarked pax.	Total pax.
Domestic scheduled	252	10.057	9.985	20.423
Domestic non-scheduled	157	148	233	381
International scheduled	933	45.457	43.895	89.352
International non-scheduled	440	7.692	7.853	15.545

The variety of leisure forms at the seashore can attract many tourists: archaeological objectives, the Danube channels and Delta, fishing settlements and the seaside resorts, etc. During the winter, reduced traffic figures are on count of closing of the summer season. The number of tourists at the seashore could increase up to 40% by 2019, since Blue Air, the airport's dominant airline opened an operational base in 2017, bringing tourists from the country and supporting the development of passenger traffic at MKIA.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The authors will focus on proposing measures for reducing the environment impact by an improvement in passenger transport infrastructure amendment in order to transform the airport into an intermodal node; since the analysis carried above showed that cargo development opportunities are reduced. For cargo considerations, an extensive port investment study will be required for its economic and societal valences.

Romania has insufficiently valorized touristic potential. In the analyzed area, tourist activity can also be associated with medical treatments (eg. heliomarine or mud treatments). By capitalizing tourism, the region would have an important source of income for the development of access path infrastructure. Thus, the authors propose to boost tourist activity by improving infrastructure and taking measures for better administrative organization.

Constanța is a destination with a low national accessibility, especially for cities like Oradea, Cluj-Napoca, Iași, etc. where road accessibility is also less attractive. The airport's infrastructure supports any type of aircraft in categories A-E, and since statistics show an upward trend for passenger traffic, MKIA must improve its services to provide passengers a seamless experience. In this concern, the lack of automated parking system or integrated passenger information system should be classified as weaknesses, and measures should be taken to improve these aspects. Despite the ideal positioning and obvious economic potential, MKIA faces some issues in investing in an efficient intermodal network inasmuch as Romania has to respect the agreement with NATO, which involves the respective area.

A development strategy regarding constructing a new railway and a multimodal terminal should consider attracting a larger number of line/charter flights during the summer, since passenger traffic is far below the airport's capacity. MKIA, located 26 km North from Constanța, is the farthest airport in Romania from the city served. This route can be done on A4 and DN2A/E60, DN39/E87 & DN2A/E60 and DN3C & DN2A/E60. The time spend on

the road by car is 24-30 min, travelling with a 68km/h speed; this trip would cost 12 RON¹⁷. Passengers can also travel by taxi, rent-a-car, minibuses or use the services of a private company specialized in transfers from the airport (Direct-Aeroport). In the last case, prices are about twelve times higher than the trip with the passenger's own car (i.e. 140 RON).

The majority of airlines at the airport are low-cost carriers. This establishes the profile of MKIA passenger, which is a cost-sensitive one, but who would appreciate more comfort and a faster transport network to the town centre or Southern resorts. The average age of MKIA passengers is between 25-45 years. The authors propose to focus on meeting passengers' expectations for the ones who choose to fly with a legacy carrier or a low-cost one.

Intermodal transport should involve the use of more than road transport (in the actual case), for passenger transfer from the airport. The authors propose that accessibility should be achieved for the national tourist resorts in the south: Olimp, Neptun, Venus, Saturn, Mangalia. This mirrors 80 km, 1h 52 min. distance by road, with no direct connection by rail. Currently, the train only links Constanța with Mangalia; the passengers would therefore have to cross the route MK Airport-Constanța by taxi or bus, and then switch to rail in order to arrive at Mangalia (passing through Agigea Nord, Agigea Ecluză, Eforie Nord, Eforie Sud, Tuzla, Costinești, Costinești Tabără and Neptun)¹⁸. So, the authors propose to extend the railway line from MKIA to Constanța and connect it with Mangalia, 2 Mai and Vama Veche, as a solution for the optimization of the public and intermodal transport.

Currently, the price of the train ticket at second class is 8.35 RON from Nicolae Bălcescu to Constanța (via Medgidia), or 7.2 RON for direct route¹⁸. This is a 34 km distance by road, which can be crossed in minimum 29 min, with a cost of 15 RON. On the other hand, the connection between Constanța and the southern resorts mirrors a 52 km/49 min minimum/23 RON by car; or a train trip with the destination Mangalia, costing 6.8 RON, with duration of 1h and 7 min, to 1h and 12 min, continued by car or minibusses for other 9.4 km.

At this point, the missing parts of the puzzle mirror the distance between the airport's terminal and Nicolae Bălcescu train station, and the one from Mangalia to Vama Veche. An analysis of the distance and prices for the two railway sections that will be added shows 10.2 km from MKIA Terminal-Nicolae Bălcescu and ticket prices from 3.9 RON to 14.4 RON, respectively 9.4 km from Mangalia to Vama Veche, with a price range of 3.9-11.1 RON¹⁸.

The analysis of the activities carried out at the airport's region and the impact it may have on the environment are meant to provide a better understanding on how to achieve sustainable development. This development will ensure that the transport system will meet economic, social and environmental needs whilst minimizing its undesirable impacts². An airport of the future considers intermodal optimization and environmental constraints.

Aviation is responsible for a marginal percentage of CO₂. While road produces 74% of CO₂, air transport is liable for a low figure of all human-induced CO₂ (2%)¹².

Fig. 4 Greenhouse emissions in various transport modes (based on ICCT data¹³)

Regarding greenhouse emissions, fig. 4 indicates that the outcome of intermodal transport growth will be reflected in environmental factors, since the variant chosen by the authors for

the development of combined transport modes considers minimizing the use of road transport, which implies many advantages: increased comfort due to a shorter journey or reduced traffic congestion, lower prices for the trip, lower levels of pollution and higher awareness of societal responsibility.

The study of the internal/external environment of the airport was carried for implementing environmental policy and solutions for respecting the principles of sustainable development. Legal aspects regarding environmental protection on railway lines (both existing and new) are in accordance with the European regulations¹. The analysis for the level of CO_2 emissions of two transport means on the distances proposed for the extension of the train line show that sustainable transportation provides solutions for efficient transport and logistics (table 3).

Table 3. Analysis of CO_2 emissions for road/rail on considered distances

Transport mean	Car	Train
CO_2 emission (g/km*pax)	42	14
CO_2 emissions MKIA Terminal-Nicolae Bălcescu	428,4	142,8
CO_2 emissions Mangalia-Vama Veche	394,8	131,6

CO_2 car emission (42 g/km*pax) are three times higher than train emissions¹⁴. Thus, adapting to multimodal commuting from air to rail services, rather than road transport, will provide an optimal network that meets the needs for mobility and durable development.

During the construction/modernization phases of the railway between the airport and Nicolae Bălcescu train station, and from Mangalia to Vama Veche, construction machinery activity, dust released into the atmosphere, waste generated by site activities, noise pollutants, etc. will be of short duration. Limiting the duration of construction works would be one of the ways to minimize environmental impact. Also, the proposal for parallel road-rail layout proved to be the best design solution for route pollution minimization. What is of interest is the expected impact during the exploitation period, although the emission of pollutants is lower than the calculated limits of emissions during construction.

A better coordination of the transport modes should consider the impact on water, air, soil or biodiversity. In the airport's area, RAJA water supply network is used for consumption, fire fighting, etc., while the discharge of water after use is done in the airport's own sewer system. Following the proposed measures related to the improvement of the intermodal network, the pollution of the sewage water from the specific airport activities (de-icing, accidental spills of oils and fuels, etc.), will be added to the use of combined transport modes.

Within the airport there is an "Ornithological Study for Wildlife", a study on the biodiversity of the airport area which includes an analysis of avifauna and large mammals on the territory and within a 5 km radius of the airport. The program will monitor the structure of the fauna and flora found in the area, so strong noises will not be agreed.

The authors also propose proper rail network maintenance and selective collection of waste. In this concern, the Internal Prevention and Protection Service of MKIA deals with the implementation of selective collection of waste generated in the airport area¹⁰. In order to protect the environment and reduce waste disposal, collection is done on a contractual basis, waste management being done according to quality management system procedures¹¹.

The airport has a collaboration protocol in the field of collection, recycling and recovery of packaging waste and recyclable industrial waste no. 2162 /11.09.2014, with M.M. RECICLYNG, collaboration protocols no. 808/24.06.2009 with RECOLAMP Association and no. 4497/10.10.2011 with ECOTIC Association for the collection of electrical and electronic waste, and a service contract no. 2201/28.10.2014 with S.C. Public Maintenance Services S.R.L. for the collection and transport of household and biodegradable waste¹⁵. In addition, through the "International Day of Tourism" program, every year on September 27,

MKIA has a #TravelEnjoyRespect campaign which encourages tourists to treat the nature, the culture of the visited countries and the local communities with respect¹⁵.

CONCLUSIONS

The paper emphasizes that a coherent policy of promoting tourism in the area must be achieved; the frequent changes and incoherence of the strategies for the development of air transport in Romania must be eliminated and programs for the development of regional airports offering subsidies for the modernization and optimization of the airport activity must exist. Constanța offers beautiful tourist attractions, meets the needs of cheap health services which are attracting Western Europeans and has the potential to promote Romanian education through foreign students who can study in universities with small tuition fee.

The authors reviewed economic, social and environmental implications of creating an intermodal transport network. The measures proposed are meant to stimulate investments and promote tourism, actions that lead to an increase in the number of jobs in the region. Furthermore, pollution reduction will be achieved through a multimodal transport solution.

As research prospects, a collaboration with the Marine Institute is aimed, an analysis on the construction of an electric railway line from the airport, examination of the issues raised by combined transport and proposals for ecological tourism development will be achieved.

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